

Synthesis and biological screening of new 2-azetidinones and 4-thiazolidinones

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4-Aryl-1-[2'-(2'',4'',6''-trichlorophenoxy)methyl]-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl]-3-chloro-2-azetidinone (**4a-j**) and 2-phenyl-3-[2'-(2'',4'',6''-trichlorophenoxy)methyl]-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl]-5-substituted-4-thiazolidinone (**5a-j**) have been synthesized from their Schiff bases (**3a-j**). They have been assayed for antibacterial and antimycobacterial activities.

1,3,4-Thiadiazoles nucleus¹ with *N*-benzylidene derivatives or heterocyclic ring system are associated with diverse biocidal activities². Various 2-azetidinones³ and 4-thiazolidinones⁴ show a variety of pharmacological and microbiological activities such as CNS, CVS, antibacterial, analgesic, antifungal etc. Moreover some derivatives of 2,3-diaryl-1,3-thiazolidin-4-ones have been proved to be highly effective in inhibiting HIV-1 replication at nanomolar concentration thereby acting as a nonnucleosides HIV-1 inhibitors (NNRTIs)⁵. These observations prompted us to synthesise the title compounds with presumption that incorporation of thiadiazole with thiazolidinone and azetidinone nuclei would produce new compounds with significant antibacterial and antimycobacterial activity.

Reaction of ethyl-2,4,6-trichlorophenoxyacetate with thiosemicarbazide using POCl₃ as cyclizing agent, gave 2-(2',4',6'-trichlorophenoxy)methyl)-5-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**2**), which is on reaction with aromatic aldehyde yielded Schiff bases (**3**). 4-Aryl-1-[2'-(2'',4'',6''-trichlorophenoxy)methyl]-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl]-3-chloro-2-azetidinone (**4a-j**) was obtained by the cycloaddition of chloroacetylchloride and trimethylamine to Schiff bases. The cycloaddition of thiolactic acid and thiomalic acid to Schiff bases yielded the corresponding 4-thiazolidinones (**5a-j**) and (**6a-j**) according to the Scheme 1 given below.

Results and discussion

Antimicrobial activity:

The compound were screened for antibacterial activity against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi* and *B. subtilis* at two test concentration in dimethyl sulphoxide by using cup-plate method⁶.

In series **4a-j**, compounds **4a,b,d,e,f,g** and **4h** were found to show mild activity at both test concentration and against

all four bacterial strains mentioned above. Compounds **4c** and **4i** were found to show mild activity against *S. typhi* at 2000 mcg ml⁻¹ concentration only, and against *B. subtilis* at both test concentration, while compound **4j** was found to show mild activity against *S. typhi* at both test concentration and against *B. subtilis* at 2000 mcg ml⁻¹ concentration only. In series **5a-j**, compound **5a** was found to show mild activity against *S. aureus* at 2000 mcg ml⁻¹ concentration

Scheme 1

and against *S. typhi* at 200 mcg ml⁻¹ concentration and compounds **5b** and **5e** were found to show mild activity against *S. typhi* at 200 mcg ml⁻¹ concentration. In series **6a-j** some compound **6a,e,f** and **6g** showed moderate activity against *B. subtilis* at 2000 mcg ml⁻¹ concentration. Ampicilin was taken for comparison purpose but compounds have not shown significant activity.

In series **5a-j**, compounds **5b,c,e,g** were tested against H₃₇Rv organism, all are found active at 100 mcg ml⁻¹ concentration. In other series compounds were found inactive against H₃₇Rv organism.

Experimental

All m.ps. were taken in open capillaries using Toshniwal apparatus and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on Shimadzu IR-460 spectrophotometer, ¹H NMR spectra on Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer with TMS as the internal standard and mass spectra on a Jeol-D-300 instrument.

Ethyl-2,4,6-trichlorophenoxy acetate (**1**): A mixture of 2,4,6-trichlorophenol (0.01 mol) and ethylchloroacetate (0.01 mol) was refluxed in dry acetone in presence of anhydrous K₂CO₃ (0.01 mol) for 6 h and then poured onto crushed ice. Liquid product obtained was isolated by ether extraction, (80%), b.p. 197°; ν_{\max} 1745 (C=O), 1050 and 1260 (C-O-C), 860–880 (tetra-sub. benzene), 800 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ (DMSO) 2.95 (2H, OCH₂), 1.49 (3H, CH₃), 4.12 (2H, CH₂), 7.51 (2H, Ar-H), 9.82 (1H, NH).

2-(2',4',6'-Trichlorophenoxyethyl)-5-amino-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**2**): A mixture of **1** (0.01 mol) thiosemicarbazide (0.012 mol) and POCl₃ (0.012 mol) was warmed at 60° for 1 h and temperature raised to 90–95° for an additional 1.5 h. The contents were then poured on to crushed ice cooled to 10°, the pH adjusted 9–10 with 10 M NaOH and resulting solid was crystallised from dioxane-DMF (3 : 1) solvent (65%); m.p. 105°; ν_{\max} 3225 (NH₂), 1570 (C=N), 1045 and 1250 (C-O-C), 830–880 (tetra-sub. benzene), 810 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ (DMSO) 3.433 (2H, OCH₂), 5.82 (2H, NH₂), 7.51 (2H, Ar-H).

2-(2',4',6'-Trichlorophenoxyethyl)-5-(N-benzylidene)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (**3a**): A mixture of **2** (0.01 mol), ethanol (95%, 30 ml) and benzaldehyde (0.01 mol) was refluxed on water bath at 90° for 6 h. The contents were then poured onto crushed ice. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from DMF (60%); m.p. 130°; ν_{\max} 3080–3030 (=C-H), 1670–1680 (C=N), 1450–1460 (CH₂), 1050 and 1260 (C-O-C), 840–850 (tetra-sub. benzene), 790–800 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl); δ (DMSO) 3.34 (2H, Ar-OCH₂-Ar), 5.06 (1H, N=CH-Ar), 7.52 (2H, Ar-H), 7.87–8.31 (4H, Ar-H). All

other compounds (**3b-j**) were prepared by similar procedure (yields 55–70%): **3b**, m.p. 155°; **c**, 150°; **d**, 164°; **e**, 175°; **f**, 148°; **g**, 168°; **h**, 151°; **i**, 160°; **j**, 125°.

4-Phenyl-1-[2'-(2'',4'',6''-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl]-3-chloro-2-azetidinone (**4a**): A solution of **3a** (0.01 mol) in dry dioxane was added to a well stirred mixture of chloroacetylchloride (0.012 mol) and triethylamine (0.012 mol) in dry dioxane. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 24 h and kept for 2 days at RT. The product was isolated and crystallized from ethanol (59%), m.p. 180°; ν_{\max} 2900 (=C-H), 1735 (C=O, azetidinone), 1600–1645 (C=N, thiadiazole), 1250–1246 and 1084–1061 (C-O-C), 899–894 (tetra-sub. benzene), 779–783 (C-Cl), 621–671 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ (DMSO) **4d**: 3.433 (2H, s, Ar-O-CH₂-Ar), 8.139 (1H, d, N-CH), 8.170 (1H, d, CH-Cl), 8.228 (2H, s, Ar-H), 7.818 (4H, m, Ar-H); *m/z* 484, 456, 458, 425, 427, 395, 283, 141, 127, 116, 77, 63.

All other compounds (**4b-j**) were prepared by similar procedure (yields 50–68%): **4b**, m.p. 230°; **c**, 175°; **d**, 154°; **e**, 228°; **f**, 198°; **g**, 210°; **h**, 202°; **i**, 195°; **j**, 169°.

2-Phenyl-3-[2'-(2'',4'',6''-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl]-5-methyl-4-thiazolidinone (**5a**): A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) and thiolactic acid (0.01 mol) was heated at 120–125° for 12 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and treated with 10% NaHCO₃ solution. The product was isolated and crystallized from ethanol (68%); m.p. 140°; ν_{\max} 3000–2950 (CH₂), 1760–1740 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1600–1605 (C=N), 1220 and 1050–1010 (C-O-C), 870–820 (1,4-sub. benzene), 810 (C-Cl), 600–620 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ (DMSO) **5b**: 3.339 (2H, s, Ar-O-CH₂-Ar), 8.108 (1H, s, N-CH), 8.300 (1H, q, CH-CH₃), 2.500 (3H, s, CH-CH₃), 8.470 (2H, s, Ar-H), 7.329–7.492 (4H, m, Ar-H); *m/z* 484, 208, 115, 103, 92, 77, 64.

All other compounds (**5b-j**) were prepared by similar procedure (yields 49–79%): **5b**, m.p. 208°; **c**, 218°; **d**, 192°; **e**, 225°; **f**, 165°; **g**, 170°; **h**, 178°; **i**, 185°; **j**, 210°.

2-Phenyl-3-[2'-(2'',4'',6''-trichlorophenoxyethyl)-1',3',4'-thiadiazol-5'-yl]-5-carboxymethyl-4-thiazolidinone (**6a**): A mixture of **3a** (0.01 mol) and thiomalic acid (0.01 mol) was heated at 160° for 2–4 h. The temperature was then raised to 180° for 30 min. The product was dissolved in NaHCO₃ solution and reprecipitated by 10% hydrochloric acid and crystallized from ethanol (65%), m.p. 148°; ν_{\max} 3660–3650 (COOH), 2975–2990 (CH₂), 1700 (C=O, thiazolidinone), 1600–1605 (C=N), 1265–1225 and 1080–1070 (C-O-C), 870–825 (1,4-sub. benzene), 820–810 (C-Cl), 620 cm⁻¹ (C-S-C); δ (DMSO) **6b**: 3.338 (2H, s, Ar-O-CH₂-Ar), 8.103 (1H, s, N-CH-), 7.596 (1H, t, CH-CH₂COOH), 3.315 (2H, aryl acid, d, CH-CH₂COOH), 8.460

(2H, s, Ar-H), 7.620–8.030, 8.410 (4H, m, Ar-H); m/z 298, 253, 209, 196, 198, 200, 202, 176, 163, 103, 92, 85, 64.

All other compounds (**6b-j**) were prepared by similar procedure (yields 45–68%): **6b**, m.p. 222°; **c**, 210°; **d**, 158°; **e**, 215°; **f**, 170°; **g**, 175°; **h**, 190°; **i**, 165°; **j**, 160°.

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